

Research Article

Bibliometric Analysis of Chronic Acromioclavicular Joint Dislocations

Hakan Batuhan KAYA¹ ¹Department of Orthopaedics and Traumatology, Umraniye Training and Research Hospital, Istanbul, Turkey

ARTICLE INFO

Article history:

Submitted January 4

Accepted February 3

Publication March 30

Keywords:

Acromioclavicular Joint

Chronic, Bibliometric Analysis

Traumatology

Citation Trends

ORCID iDs of the

Corresponding:

Hakan Batuhan KAYA

0000-0002-9788-6578

ABSTRACT

Objective:

This study aimed to bibliometrically analyze the most highly cited publications on the diagnosis and treatment of chronic acromioclavicular joint dislocations, identifying research trends, leading journals, contributing countries, and levels of evidence.

Methods:

In November 2025, a comprehensive literature search was conducted in the Web of Science Core Collection database to identify publications related to chronic AC joint dislocations. After applying predefined inclusion and exclusion criteria, the 50 most-cited original articles were selected for analysis. Bibliometric parameters including publication year, journal, country of origin, authorship contribution, total and annual citation counts, study design, and levels of evidence were evaluated.

Results:

The 50 studies published between 1998 and 2021 accumulated a total of 2,685 citations, with a mean of 53.7 citations per article. The highest number of publications appeared in *Arthroscopy – The Journal of Arthroscopic and Related Surgery*, *The American Journal of Sports Medicine*, and *Knee Surgery, Sports Traumatology, Arthroscopy*. The United States ranked first in terms of both publication output and total citation count. Clinical studies accounted for 98% of the included articles, with the majority classified as Level IV evidence. The most frequently investigated topics were surgical treatment strategies and ligament reconstruction techniques.

Conclusion:

This bibliometric analysis shows that research on chronic acromioclavicular joint dislocations is largely focused on surgical management and is dominated by studies with low levels of evidence. These findings underscore the need for high-quality, prospective, multicenter studies to strengthen the evidence base and guide future research.

Doi:

Introduction

Acromioclavicular (AC) joint injuries account for approximately 9–10% of shoulder girdle traumas and are most commonly encountered in young and physically active individuals between 20 and 40 years of age. These injuries typically occur as a result of high-energy mechanisms, such as contact sports, or direct falls onto the shoulder (Albishi et al., 2024; Nolte et al., 2020). When not effectively treated in the acute phase, or when managed conservatively in selected cases, chronic dislocation may develop over time. Chronic AC joint dislocations can lead to persistent pain, functional impairment, and cosmetic deformity, thereby negatively affecting daily activities and overall quality of life (Nolte et al., 2020).

The evaluation of AC joint injuries is commonly based on the Rockwood classification system. According to this classification, dislocations classified as Types III to V are associated with a higher risk of long-term instability (Rockwood, 2009). Injuries are generally considered chronic once a period of 3 to 6 weeks has elapsed following the initial trauma. Beyond this timeframe, the biological healing potential of the coracoclavicular ligaments diminishes, rendering management more complex (Nolte et al., 2020; Weinstein et al., 1995). The literature emphasizes that ligament healing becomes limited after approximately the third week, and therefore reconstructive techniques are more frequently advocated in chronic cases (Nolte

et al., 2020; Weinstein et al., 1995). Consequently, surgical intervention is recommended more often for chronic AC joint dislocations than for acute injuries, with procedures providing biomechanical stabilization such as ligament reconstruction being commonly employed (Cisneros & Reiriz, 2017; Nolte et al., 2020; Weinstein et al., 1995). In the diagnostic workup, anteroposterior (AP) shoulder radiographs and Zanca views are routinely used, typically with bilateral comparison. Axial or stress radiographs may assist in identifying horizontal instability. When necessary, computed tomography (CT) allows detailed assessment of osseous anatomy, while magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) plays a critical role in evaluating ligament integrity as well as associated soft-tissue pathologies, including the deltoid fascia and rotator cuff (Albishi et al., 2024). Despite extensive research, there is no clear consensus in the literature regarding the optimal management of chronic AC joint dislocations. Surgical options include open and arthroscopic approaches, anatomic and non-anatomic reconstructions, and the use of synthetic ligaments, autografts, or allografts (Cisneros & Reiriz, 2017; Muench et al., 2019; Nolte et al., 2020). However, the relative superiority of these techniques, the ideal timing of surgical intervention, and long-term clinical outcomes remain subjects of ongoing debate (Muench et al., 2019; Nolte et al., 2020). To better understand the existing body of knowledge on this clinical condition, bibliometric evaluation of the most highly cited studies is particularly valuable.

Corresponding author:

Hakan Batuhan KAYA
hbatuhan-kaya-
123@hotmail.com

Such analyses can elucidate research trends, methodological patterns, prominent journals, and existing knowledge gaps based on publication timelines and citation metrics (O'Dwyer et al., 2025). Accordingly, the aim of this study was to identify the 50 most-cited articles in the literature addressing the diagnosis and treatment of chronic acromioclavicular joint dislocations and to analyze these publications from a bibliometric perspective.

Materials and Methods

Ethical approval was not required for this bibliometric analysis, as the study did not involve direct participation of human subjects or animals. In November 2025, a comprehensive literature search was conducted using the Web of Science Citation Database to identify the most highly cited scientific publications related to chronic acromioclavicular (AC) joint dislocations. The search was performed using the following Web of Science topic search string: TS = ("acromioclavicular joint" AND (dislocation OR separation OR injury) AND chronic). The search was limited to publications written in English, with no restrictions applied regarding publication year.

The retrieved results were sorted in descending order according to citation count, with more recently published articles prioritized in cases of identical citation numbers. Initial screening was performed at the title and abstract level, and full texts were reviewed when relevance was uncertain. Inclusion criteria were as follows: (1) publication in a peer-reviewed journal, (2) primary focus on chronic AC joint dislocation, and (3) original research involving primary data. Exclusion criteria included: (1) review articles, systematic reviews, and/or meta-analyses; (2) cadaveric studies, biomechanical experiments, and anatomical investigations; and (3) conference abstracts, technical notes, editorials, and publications with inaccessible full texts.

After application of all exclusion criteria, the 50 most-cited articles meeting the inclusion criteria were included in the final dataset for analysis. These publications were evaluated according to bibliometric variables including publication year, author(s), country of origin, journal, institution, total citation count, study type, and level of evidence. Levels of evidence were determined according to the orthopedic classification system recommended by The Journal of Bone and Joint Surgery (Wright et al., 2003). In addition, the annual citation density for each article was calculated by dividing the total number of citations by the number of years since publication.

The included studies were categorized into two main groups: clinical studies and basic science studies. Clinical studies were further classified as diagnostic, therapeutic, or prognostic, whereas basic science studies were subcategorized based on anatomical, radiological, or biomechanical content. Clinical investigations were further analyzed with respect to sample size, follow-up duration, patient demographics, treatment modalities, and outcome measures.

Results

The applied search strategy initially yielded 261 articles. Of these, 164 records were excluded after title and abstract screening due to irrelevance, duplication, or non-original study design. During the preliminary screening process, the remaining 97 studies were assessed in detail. Subsequently, 47 articles were excluded in descending order of citation count to establish the final list of the 50 most-cited publications (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Study Selection Flowchart.

The included studies were published between 1998 and 2021, appeared in 22 different journals, and were authored by 243 individual researchers. Among these journals, Knee Surgery, Sports Traumatology, Arthroscopy was the most prolific, publishing eight articles, followed by Arthroscopy – The Journal of Arthroscopic and Related Surgery with seven articles and The American Journal of Sports Medicine with six articles (Figure 2). Articles published in The American Journal of Sports Medicine demonstrated notably high citation values, with the highest single-article citation count reaching 189. Arthroscopy and Knee Surgery, Sports Traumatology, Arthroscopy also constituted a substantial contribution to the literature in terms of both publication volume and total citation impact.

Citation counts of the selected studies ranged from 17 to 189, with a mean of 53.7 citations per article. The cumulative citation count of the 50 included publications was 2,685. The top 10 most-cited articles collectively accounted for 1,104 citations, representing a substantial proportion of total citations. In terms of authorship contribution, Tauber et al. were identified as contributors to the study with the highest single citation count (n = 189) (Table 1).

Table 1. The 10 Most Cited Studies on Chronic Acromioclavicular Joint Dislocations

No	Studies	Citation count	Citations per year
1	Tauber M, Gordon K, Koller H, Fox M, Resch H. Semitendinosus tendon graft versus a modified Weaver-Dunn procedure for acromioclavicular joint reconstruction in chronic cases: a prospective comparative study. <i>Am J Sports Med.</i> 2009 Jan;37(1):181-90. doi: 10.1177/0363546508323255. PMID: 18818433.	189	11.1
2	Tauber M, Valler D, Lichtenberg S, Magosch P, Moroder P, Habermeyer P. Arthroscopic Stabilization of Chronic Acromioclavicular Joint Dislocations: Triple-Versus Single-Bundle Reconstruction. <i>Am J Sports Med.</i> 2016 Feb;44(2):482-9. doi: 10.1177/0363546515615583. PMID: 26657259.	155	8.6
3	Boileau P, Old J, Gstaald O, Brassart N, Roussanne Y. All-arthroscopic Weaver-Dunn-Chuinard procedure with double-button fixation for chronic acromioclavicular joint dislocation. <i>Arthroscopy.</i> 2010 Feb;26(2):149-60. doi: 10.1016/j.arthro.2009.08.008. PMID: 20141978.	124	5.6
4	Guy DK, Wirth MA, Griffin JL, Rockwood CA Jr. Reconstruction of chronic and complete dislocations of the acromioclavicular joint. <i>Clin Orthop Relat Res.</i> 1998 Feb;(347):138-49. PMID: 9520884.	109	10.9
5	Yoo JC, Ahn JH, Yoon JR, Yang JH. Clinical results of single-tunnel coracoclavicular ligament reconstruction using autogenous semitendinosus tendon. <i>Am J Sports Med.</i> 2010 May;38(5):950-7. doi: 10.1177/0363546509356976. PMID: 20228243.	105	6.6
6	Guy DK, Wirth MA, Griffin JL, Rockwood CA Jr. Reconstruction of chronic and complete dislocations of the acromioclavicular joint. <i>Clin Orthop Relat Res.</i> 1998 Feb;(347):138-49. PMID: 9520884.	93	3.3
7	Yoo JC, Ahn JH, Yoon JR, Yang JH. Clinical results of single-tunnel coracoclavicular ligament reconstruction using autogenous semitendinosus tendon. <i>Am J Sports Med.</i> 2010 May;38(5):950-7. doi: 10.1177/0363546509356976. PMID: 20228243.	90	5.6
8	Alyas F, Curtis M, Speed C, Saifuddin A, Connell D. MR imaging appearances of acromioclavicular joint dislocation. <i>Radiographics.</i> 2008 Mar-Apr;28(2):463-79; quiz 619. doi: 10.1148/rg.282075714. PMID: 18349451.	83	4.6
9	Rosso C, Martetschläger F, Saccomanno MF, Voss A, Lacheta L; ESA DELPHI Consensus Panel; Beitzel K, Milano G. High degree of consensus achieved regarding diagnosis and treatment of acromioclavicular joint instability among ESA-ESSKA members. <i>Knee Surg Sports Traumatol Arthrosc.</i> 2021 Jul;29(7):2325-2332. doi: 10.1007/s00167-020-06286-w. PMID: 33225517.	82	16.4
10	Lafosse L, Baier GP, Leuzinger J. Arthroscopic treatment of acute and chronic acromioclavicular joint dislocation. <i>Arthroscopy.</i> 2005 Aug;21(8):1017. doi: 10.1016/j.arthro.2005.05.034. PMID: 16086572.	74	3.5

Figure 2. Distribution of publications by journal.

Year-based analysis revealed that 2010 was the most productive year, with six publications. In contrast, although fewer articles were published in 2009 (four publications), this year achieved the highest total citation count, with 438 citations. Additionally, a distinct cluster of highly cited publications was observed between 2013 and 2015, comprising a total of 11 studies. More recently published articles (2019–2021) demonstrated an increase in publication volume but relatively lower citation counts (Figure 3).

Figure 3. Publication and citation counts by year.

Geographical analysis indicated that the United States was the leading contributing country by a considerable margin, accounting for both the highest number of publications (n = 39) and the greatest total number of citations (n = 2,083). The United Kingdom ranked second with five publications and 239 citations, followed by the Netherlands, Belgium, Italy, and France. Publications originating from the United States achieved the highest mean citation rate per article (58.6 citations).

All of the 50 most-cited publications were original research articles, and no review articles were included. Of these studies, 49 were classified as clinical research and one as a basic science study. Analysis of levels of evidence among the clinical studies demonstrated that four articles provided Level I evidence, eight provided Level II evidence, six provided Level III evidence, and 32 provided Level IV evidence.

Discussion

Bibliometric analyses are valuable tools that enable objective evaluation of scientific productivity, research impact, and developmental trends within a specific field. This approach facilitates the systematic identification of influential studies, dominant research themes, and existing knowledge gaps in the literature.

Accordingly, bibliometric studies focusing on specific clinical problems contribute to a deeper understanding of the available evidence and provide a guiding framework for future research (Dünki, 2025).

The present bibliometric analysis demonstrates that research on chronic AC joint dislocations has undergone a notable evolution over time. The increase in both publication volume and citation counts observed from 2010 onward indicates growing academic interest in this clinical condition. The continued citation of earlier seminal studies suggests that these publications not only hold historical significance but also continue to play a foundational role in shaping contemporary clinical practice.

From a geographical perspective, the United States emerged as the dominant contributor in terms of both publication volume and total citation count. European countries followed, with particularly notable contributions from the United Kingdom, the Netherlands, and Belgium. Despite producing fewer publications, some European countries achieved relatively high average citation rates per article, indicating a strong scientific impact of their work within this field.

Analysis of research focus revealed that the majority of studies concentrated on surgical treatment strategies. Single- and double-bundle fixation techniques, hook plate fixation, and anatomic and non-anatomic coracoclavicular ligament reconstructions were among the most frequently investigated surgical approaches (Guy et al., 1998; Tauber et al., 2016; Tauber et al., 2009). The presence of highly cited studies evaluating anatomic reconstruction techniques reflects the growing influence of modern surgical concepts aimed at restoring native biomechanics (Tauber et al., 2016). Nevertheless, the diversity of surgical techniques reported in the literature underscores the lack of consensus regarding the optimal treatment strategy for chronic AC joint dislocation.

Evaluation of study designs highlighted the predominance of case series. The fact that a substantial proportion of the 50 most-cited articles provided Level IV evidence indicates that high-level scientific evidence addressing chronic AC joint dislocations remains limited. This finding emphasizes the need for more robust study designs to strengthen the evidence base in this field.

Journal-based analysis demonstrated that research on chronic AC joint dislocations is largely concentrated within a relatively small number of high-impact factor sports medicine and shoulder surgery journals. This centralization of scientific output suggests that knowledge dissemination in this field is driven primarily by select specialty journals. The prominence of journals such as Arthroscopy – The Journal of Arthroscopic and Related Surgery further indicates that AC joint injuries are frequently discussed in the context of sports-related injury mechanisms and arthroscopic treatment techniques.

Several limitations of this study should be acknowledged. First, the bibliometric evaluation was conducted exclusively using the Web of Science Core Collection database, which may have resulted in the exclusion of relevant studies indexed in other databases. Second, the inclusion of only English-language publications may have introduced language bias and led to the omission of potentially valuable non-English studies. Finally, limiting the analysis to the 50 most-cited articles may have underrepresented methodologically rigorous studies with lower citation counts.

Conclusion

This bibliometric analysis demonstrates that the literature on chronic acromioclavicular joint dislocation is predominantly focused on surgical treatment strategies and is concentrated within a limited number of high-impact journals. The majority of influential studies are characterized by low levels of evidence, highlighting important methodological limitations in the existing body of research. These findings underscore the need for high-quality, multicenter, prospective studies with improved methodological rigor, clearer definition of patient subgroups, and standardized treatment frameworks to better inform clinical decision-making and ultimately improve patient outcomes.

Declaration of conflicting interests

The author(s) declared no potential conflicts of interest with respect to the research, authorship, and/or publication of this article

Funding

The author(s) received no financial support for the research, authorship, and/or publication of this article.

Ethical approval

Ethical approval was not required for this bibliometric analysis, as the study did not involve direct participation of human subjects or animals, and all data were obtained from publicly available sources

References

Albishi, W., AlShayhan, F., Alfridy, A., Alaseem, A., & Elmaraghy, A. (2024). Acromioclavicular joint separation: Controversies and treatment algorithm. *Orthop Rev (Pavia)*, 16, 94037. <https://doi.org/10.52965/001c.94037>

Cisneros, L. N., & Reiriz, J. S. (2017). Management of chronic unstable acromioclavicular joint injuries. *J Orthop Traumatol*, 18(4), 305-318. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10195-017-0452-0>

Dünki, A. (2025). Top 50 articles in sacrum fracture management: A bibliometric analysis. *TOTBID Research Journal*, 1(2), 73-79. <https://doi.org/10.5578/totbidarder.20250242>

Guy, D. K., Wirth, M. A., Griffin, J. L., & Rockwood, C. A., Jr. (1998). Reconstruction of chronic and complete dislocations of the acromioclavicular joint. *Clin Orthop Relat Res*(347), 138-149.

Muench, L. N., Kia, C., Jerliu, A., Murphy, M., Berthold, D. P., Cote, M. P., Arciero, R. A., & Mazzocca, A. D. (2019). Functional and Radiographic Outcomes After Anatomic Coracoclavicular Ligament Reconstruction for Type III/IV Acromioclavicular Joint Injuries. *Orthop J Sports Med*, 7(11), 2325967119884539. <https://doi.org/10.1177/2325967119884539>

Nolte, P. C., Lacheta, L., Dekker, T. J., Elrick, B. P., & Millett, P. J. (2020). Optimal Management of Acromioclavicular Dislocation: Current Perspectives. *Orthop Res Rev*, 12, 27-44. <https://doi.org/10.2147/orr.S218991>

O'Dwyer, L., Murphy, B., Davey, M. S., Morrissey, D., & Cassidy, J. T. (2025). A bibliometric analysis of the 50 most cited articles on acromioclavicular joint reconstruction. *Musculoskelet Surg*, 109(3), 257-265. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12306-025-00886-w>

Rockwood, C. A. (2009). *The shoulder* (Vol. 1). Elsevier Health Sciences. Tauber, M., Gordon, K., Koller, H., Fox, M., & Resch, H. (2009). Semitendinosus tendon graft versus a modified Weaver-Dunn procedure for acromioclavicular joint reconstruction in chronic cases: a prospective comparative study. *Am J Sports Med*, 37(1), 181-190. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0363546508323255>

Tauber, M., Valler, D., Lichtenberg, S., Magosch, P., Moroder, P., & Habermeyer, P. (2016). Arthroscopic Stabilization of Chronic Acromioclavicular Joint Dislocations: Triple- Versus Single-Bundle Reconstruction. *Am J Sports Med*, 44(2), 482-489. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0363546515615583>

Weinstein, D. M., McCann, P. D., McIlveen, S. J., Flatow, E. L., & Bigliani, L. U. (1995). Surgical treatment of complete acromioclavicular dislocations. *Am J Sports Med*, 23(3), 324-331. <https://doi.org/10.1177/036354659502300313>

Wright, J. G., Swiontkowski, M. F., & Heckman, J. D. (2003). Introducing levels of evidence to the journal. *J Bone Joint Surg Am*, 85(1), 1-3.